

1 **Rheological characterization and modeling of freshwater and marine microalgae and cyanobacteria**
2 **co-cultures**

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Abstract

Rheology is crucial for algal cultivation, affecting mixing efficiency and biomass productivity. There is limited research on the rheological aspects of co-cultivating algae and cyanobacteria. The study aimed to investigate the rheological properties of microalgae and cyanobacteria co-cultures (*Chlorella vulgaris* and *Microcystis aeruginosa*; *Nannochloropsis oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp.).

While all species were spherical and non-motile with similar aspect ratios, *Prochlorococcus* sp. exhibited meaningful cell-cell repulsion, increasing its apparent effective volume fraction by 20-40%. Mixed suspensions of *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa* demonstrated shear thinning at all concentrations, accurately described by a power law model across the explored shear-rate range. The conventional Einstein and Krieger-Dougherty models confirmed that viscosity increased with cell concentration, with *Prochlorococcus* sp. having the greatest impact. However, these models did not effectively account for mixed suspensions.

A novel model, based on Pal et al (2023) and incorporating two independent parameters, provided a greater reflection of the viscosity in mixed suspensions. Interestingly, parameters for this new co-culture model could be derived from mono-culture rheological models within the studied concentration range.

This first-of-its-kind study highlighted the significance of rheology in optimizing co-cultures and identifies the need for further research to address rheological challenges, notably towards higher industrial-scale biomass densities.

Key words: algae, cyanobacteria, co-cultures, mixed species rheology, viscosity model

39 **1.0 Introduction**

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40 3 The on-going exploitation of fossil fuels and increasing atmospheric carbon dioxide levels necessitate a shift
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41 5 to renewable energy sources. Microalgae, as a third-generation feedstock, provide a promising solution by
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42 7 offering alternative biomass sources for fuels and other high-value products (Khan, Shin et al. 2018), although
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4310 achieving economically viable production at commercial scale requires ongoing research efforts (Davis, Aden
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4412 et al. 2011). Recent work has highlighted the potential of co-culturing algae and bacteria for enhanced biomass
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4515 productivity (Higgins, Labavitch et al. 2015, Kim, Yun et al. 2020) or integrated wastewater treatment
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4617 (Mujtaba and Lee 2017), resulting in reduced cost of algal production systems.
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4721 In industrial settings, microalgae are typically cultivated at very low cell densities, around 0.05% w/w
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4823 (Muhammad, Alam et al. 2020), due to shading effects in photo-autotrophic growth. However, advanced
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4925 photo-bioreactors can improve light distribution, increasing biomass concentrations approximately 10-fold
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5028 (Dogaris, Welch et al. 2015). The in-depth knowledge of rheological behavior of algal suspensions is key to
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5130 improving mixing efficiency and reducing power requirements in bioprocesses. The microalgae culture
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5233 process shows time-varying rheology, starting as a low-viscosity Newtonian medium. As biomass
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5335 concentration increases, it transitions to a higher viscosity Newtonian fluid at intermediate levels and
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5438 ultimately becomes a non-Newtonian fluid at high biomass concentrations (Yatirajula, Shrivastava et al. 2019).
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5540 These transitions and the ultimate rheological properties are highly dependent on the multiple parameters
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5643 (such as volume fraction, pH of media, cell charge, extracellular polymeric substance) (Zhang, Jiang et al.
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5745 2013, Attar, Morillas-Espana et al. 2022) and the specific species (such as cell diameter, cell wall rigidity,
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5848 motility, morphology) (Adesanya, Vadillo et al. 2012, Song, Kang et al. 2018, Martínez-Sanz, Garrido-
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5950 Fernández et al. 2020) involved and remain largely unexplored. Dense suspensions vary in shear stress with
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6052 shear rates, fitting a power-law model to determine the consistency (K) and flow behavior (n) indices
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6155 (Schaschke 2014), but no specific algal cell concentration marks the Newtonian to non-Newtonian shift
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6257 (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012, dos Santos, Martins et al. 2013, Cagney, Zhang et al. 2017, Attar, Morillas-
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63 Espana et al. 2022). Viscosity models like the Einstein (Barnes 2000) and Krieger-Dougherty (Krieger and
64 1 Dougherty 1959) equations predict the effective viscosity based on particle volume fraction (ϕ) and medium
65 2 viscosity (μ_{eff}), effectively applied for dilute and concentrated suspensions, respectively.
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67 4 Our thorough literature review (Supplementary Table S1) highlights that, in mono-species cultures, viscosity
68 5 consistently increases with higher cell concentrations, validating the models used in this study (Rafai, Jibuti
69 6 et al. 2010, Mussler, Rafaï et al. 2013, Souliès, Pruvost et al. 2013, Zhang, Jiang et al. 2013, Cagney, Zhang
70 7 et al. 2017). This increase in viscosity depends on various cell properties such as morphology (Wileman,
71 8 Ozkan et al. 2012, Cagney, Zhang et al. 2017, Song, Kang et al. 2018, Martínez-Sanz, Garrido-Fernández et
72 9 al. 2020), zeta potential (Zhang, Jiang et al. 2013), cell rigidity (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012), viability (Song,
73 10 Kang et al. 2018), and motion (Genovese 2012). The predictive viscosity models mentioned above are
74 11 primarily developed for mono-species suspensions. For suspensions with mixed species, the Pal23 model (Pal
75 12 2023) offers a novel approach using two independent volume fraction terms (ϕ_1 and ϕ_2) for particles of
76 13 differing sizes, allowing for a more accurate modeling of viscosity compared to mono-species models.
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78 15 Despite the fundamental role bacteria can play in algae processes, a significant gap exists in research exploring
79 16 the complex fluid dynamics and influences of bacterial involvement on rheology. The presence of bacteria in
80 17 algae cultures can significantly alter the rheological properties of the culture medium (Belachqer-El Attar,
81 18 Morillas-Espana et al. 2023). Previous research (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012, Belachqer-El Attar, Morillas-
82 19 Espana et al. 2023) has focussed largely on monoalgal systems, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding
83 20 the rheology of co-culture systems, which is critical for maintaining symbiotic relationships, and preventing
84 21 aggregation issues in system design and operation (Caillet and Adelard 2022). Understanding and controlling
85 22 the rheological characteristics are crucial for designing efficient cultivation systems and downstream
86 23 processing techniques.
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88 25 The current study for the first time examined the rheology and flow behavior of two algae-cyanobacteria co-
89 26 cultures - freshwater *Chlorella vulgaris* and freshwater *Microcystis aeruginosa*; and marine *Nannochloropsis*
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87 *oceanica* and marine *Prochlorococcus* sp. under controlled conditions. Various concentrations of algae and
88 1 cyanobacteria cells are examined in test samples, providing insight into how rheology is affected by different
89 2 cell culture conditions. The study focuses on algae:cyanobacteria co-cultures and their potential impact on
90 3 rheological predictions. Rheological properties are investigated across monoalgal cultures, mono-
91 4 cyanobacteria cultures, and predefined algae and cyanobacteria co-culture ratios. Non-Newtonian rheological
92 5 properties were modelled using the power-law equation (Section 2.5.1), and predictive viscosity models
93 6 (Section 2.5.2) were fitted using non-linear regression. Additionally, morphological properties (Section 2.2)
94 7 were studied and correlated with viscosity, while the zeta potential properties (Section 2.4) were analysed and
95 8 correlated to the power-law model and viscosity behaviors.

96 9 **2.0 Materials and Methods**

97 10 **2.1 Microalgae and Cyanobacteria growth conditions**

98 11 Two microalgae strains were used in this study. The freshwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* (CS-41) the
99 12 marine *Nannochloropsis Oceanica* (CS-179) were obtained from the Australian National Algae Culture
100 13 Collection (CSIRO). The freshwater *C. vulgaris* was grown in MLA medium (Algaboost; Wallaroo, SA,
101 14 Australia), comprising approximately 49 mg/L of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 170 mg/L of $NaNO_3$, 35 mg/L of K_2HPO_4 ,
102 15 and 2 mg/L of H_3BO_3 , respectively (Bolch and Blackburn 1996). On the other hand, the marine *N. oceanica*
103 16 was grown in marine f/2 media (Guillard 1975), and prepared using autoclaved seawater collected from
104 17 Sydney Harbour (with a salinity of 33-35 g/L). All the seed cultures for the experiments were grown to high
105 18 density in air-sparged 2 L Schott bottles and were exposed to a constant photoperiod with a light intensity of
106 19 $60-70 \mu mol photons m^{-2} s^{-1}$. The cultures were maintained at an ambient temperature of $25 \pm 4 \text{ }^\circ C$ and were
107 20 sealed with 0.2 μm vented caps to prevent airborne contamination. Two strains of cyanobacteria selected in
108 21 this study were obtained from the Australian National Algae Culture Collection (CSIRO). The freshwater
109 22 *Microcystis aeruginosa* (CS-558) and marine *Prochlorococcus* sp. (CS-965) grown in MLA media (Bolch and

110 Blackburn 1996) and marine Pro 99 media (Moore, Coe et al. 2007), respectively under the same growth
111 1 conditions as the microalgae cultures.
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112 5 At the onset of the early stationary phase, the cultures were centrifuged (Multifuge X4 Pro, Thermo Scientific)
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114 7 at 4200 rpm for 15 minutes to obtain a cell pellet and supernatant, individually. The obtained freshwater and
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116 9 marine pellets were resuspended in a known volume of MiliQ and 3% NaCl, respectively to prepare stock
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118 11 solutions of each species, individually. The pellets and supernatant were stored at -20 °C until further use. 20
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120 13 mL samples of algal and cyanobacteria cultures were taken. Cell concentration was estimated by measuring
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122 15 the absorbance of diluted samples (Abs₆₈₀) using a 96-well plate reader (Varioskan™ LUX spectrophotometer,
123 16
124 17 Thermo Scientific). Cell density (cells/mL) for each species suspension was measured using a FACS
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126 19 instrument (Cytoflex LX Flow Cytometer, Beckman Coulter). Separate linear correlations (R² > 0.93) between
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128 21 cell concentrations (cells/mL) and absorbance were established for each species. This allowed the conversion
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130 23 of Abs₆₈₀ readings of the suspensions into cell densities (cells/mL) throughout the experiments.
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132 30 *2.2 Cell Morphology*

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134 34 Cell morphology measurements of each species suspension were conducted using a light microscope (Nikon
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136 36 Eclipse Ci-L plus, Nikon) in conjunction with ImageJ software (Schneider, Rasband et al. 2012). Briefly, a
137 37
138 38 small drop (~10 µL) of each sample was placed onto a microscopic slide and covered with a coverslip.
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141 41 Subsequently, images were captured at 100x magnification using a DP72 digital camera from Olympus
142 42
143 43 (Australia). ImageJ was used to study the various parameters such as cell shape, cell diameter, cell volume,
144 44
145 45 and aspect ratio of each species. Multiple fields of view (at least 30) were randomly selected to ensure a
146 46
147 47 representative sample. From the minor and major axes provided by ImageJ, the cell volume (V, µm³) was
148 48
149 49 calculated according to Eq. 1.
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$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi \times \frac{r_1}{2} \times \frac{r_2}{2} \times \frac{r_2}{2} \dots \dots \dots \text{(Eq.1)}$$

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132 Where, r_1 is the major axis of the cell, and r_2 is the minor axis. The cell is assumed to rotate around its minor
133 axis; therefore, the volume of prolate spheroid formula is used (Hillebrand, Dürselen et al. 1999).

134 2.3 Rheological measurements

135 The freshwater and marine co-culture combinations were prepared by mixing microalgae and cyanobacteria
136 suspensions in fixed volume ratios (1:1, 1:10, 10:1, 1:5, 5:1, v/v) to achieve the desired cell concentrations
137 ranging from 10^8 to 10^6 cells/mL. These ratios were selected to investigate a range of cell concentrations
138 suitable for co-culture systems. The volume fraction range tested varied between species due to differences in
139 cell concentrations in each culture.

140 The volume fraction (ϕ , dimensionless) of each of the individual suspensions was determined by the following
141 formula (Eq. 2):

$$142 \phi = (v_c \times C_n) \dots \dots \dots \text{(Eq. 2)}$$

143 Where, v_c is the volume of an individual cell in μm^3 , and C_n is the number of cells/mL in the suspension. The
144 volume of 1 mL of water was converted to μm^3 for calculations to obtain a dimensionless unit. To calculate
145 the total volume fraction of the mixed suspension, the volume fractions of the two component suspensions
146 were added together.

147 *C. vulgaris* suspensions had volume fractions (ϕ) ranging from 0.0029 to 0.027, *N. oceanica* from 0.0015 to
148 0.015, *M. aeruginosa* from 0.00026 to 0.0044, and *Prochlorococcus* sp. from 9.3×10^{-7} to 1.21×10^{-5} . The
149 much lower values are attributed to the significantly smaller size of *Prochlorococcus* sp. However, as will be
150 demonstrated in the results section, the effective volume fraction, when considering for zeta potential effects,
151 is much higher. The controls (mono-algal, mono-cyanobacterial cultures, supernatants, and fresh media) were
152 also tested to provide a comprehensive understanding of the co-culture system dynamics. A strain-controlled
153 rheometer (Discovery Hybrid Rheometer 1, TA Instruments) with a 40 mm parallel plate and a gap height of
154 600 μm was used, equipped with (TRIOS, TA instruments) software to automatically calculate shear rate, and

155 shear stress, based on the measured torque and displacement data, following the method described by
156 ¹₂ (Martínez-Sanz, Garrido-Fernández et al. 2020). Briefly, shear rates $\dot{\gamma}$ from 0.5 s⁻¹ to 225 s⁻¹ were tested for
157 ³₄ each sample. The recorded measurements were averaged after a 2.5 second equilibration time for each shear
158 ⁵₆ rate applied to a sample. Shear stress values were averaged after an equilibration period, and samples were
159 ⁷₈ maintained at 25°C using a Peltier plate attachment. The viscosity (μ , Pa. s) for each shear rate was calculated
160 ⁹₁₀ according to Eq. 3.
161 ¹¹₁₂

$$\mu = \frac{\tau}{\dot{\gamma}} \dots\dots\dots \text{(Eq. 3)}$$

162 ¹³₁₄ Where, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate (s⁻¹), and τ is the shear stress (Pa).
163 ¹⁵₁₆
164 ¹⁷₁₈

163 ¹⁹₂₀ 2.4 Zeta potential

164 ²¹₂₂ Suspensions of all microalgae, cyanobacteria, and mixed microalgae and cyanobacteria were prepared using
165 ²³₂₄ the same cell concentrations and blanking mediums as those used for the rheology measurements. The zeta
166 ²⁵₂₆ potential of algal cells was measured using a Zetasizer Nano ZS Zen 3600 instrument (Malvern, UK). To
167 ²⁷₂₈ prevent charge screening, samples were diluted twofold. A 3 mL aliquot of each sample was transferred into
168 ²⁹₃₀ DTS1070 disposable folded capillary cells. The refractive index used for the measurements was 1.347, deemed
169 ³¹₃₂ most suitable for assessing the surface charge of microalgae (Aditya, Vu et al. 2024). With a dielectric constant
170 ³³₃₄ of 78.5, water was used as the dispersant. The measurements were conducted at a controlled temperature of
171 ³⁵₃₆ 25°C. For each sample, three measurements were performed, each consisting of 100 runs, ensuring that
172 ³⁷₃₈ standard errors were maintained below 2.0%. Zeta potentials were calculated and selected for precision,
173 ³⁹₄₀ considering the cell size and ionic strength of the media.
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174 ⁴³₄₄ 2.5 Data analysis

175 ⁴⁵₄₆ 2.5.1 Power-Law

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177 ⁵¹₅₂
178 ⁵³₅₄
179 ⁵⁵₅₆
180 ⁵⁷₅₈
181 ⁵⁹₆₀
182 ⁶¹₆₂
183 ⁶³₆₄
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176 The flow behavior was quantified by fitting the appropriate range of shear rate and shear stress data collected
 177 for each species to the Power-Law model (Eq. 4) (Schaschke 2014), from which the flow behavior index (n)
 178 and the consistency index (K) was determined.

$$179 \tau = K \times \dot{\gamma}^n \dots\dots\dots \text{(Eq. 4)}$$

180 This model was fit using the curve_fit function from the Python package Sci-Py (Virtanen, Gommers et al.
 181 2020).

182 When $n = 1$, the flow is Newtonian, and the viscosity does not change with varying shear rate. Conversely,
 183 when $n < 1$, the flow is shear-thinning, and the viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate. This shear-
 184 thinning behavior is typically observed as cell concentration increases above a threshold value, where cell-
 185 cell interactions begin to occur. The threshold value varies across species and depends on various factors such
 186 as rigidity (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012), morphology (Cagney, Zhang et al. 2017), zeta potential (Zhang,
 187 Jiang et al. 2013), and EPS production (Belachqer-El Attar, Morillas-Espana et al. 2023), typically the
 188 threshold lies somewhere between $\phi = 0.015 - 0.1$ (Supplementary Table S1).

189 **2.5.2 Viscosity models**

190 The relationship between viscosity (at 100 s^{-1}) and volume fraction was analysed by fitting the Einstein (1905,
 191 Eq. 5) (Barnes 2000) and Krieger-Dougherty (1959, Eq. 6) (Krieger and Dougherty 1959) models to this data.

$$192 \mu_r = \mu_0(1 + \alpha\phi) \dots\dots\dots \text{(Eq. 5)}$$

$$193 \mu_r = \mu_0 \left(1 + \frac{\phi}{\phi_m}\right)^{-\alpha\phi_m} \dots\dots\dots \text{(Eq. 6)}$$

194 Where, μ_r is the relative viscosity, μ_0 is the viscosity of the cell-free suspending medium, ϕ_m is assumed to
 195 be around 0.62, as in previous studies on the viscosity of microalgae (Rafai, Jibuti et al. 2010). However, this

196 value depends on the shape and morphological distribution of the cells within the suspension (Wouterse,
197 1 Williams et al. 2007, Farr 2013).
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198 5 The novel viscosity model Pal23 (Pal 2023) was used to calculate the viscosity of suspensions with multiple
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199 7 distinct particle types (Eq. 7). This model is like the Krieger-Dougherty model but uses two independent
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200 9 volume fraction terms: ϕ_1 for the volume fraction of the first species (here algae) and ϕ_2 for the volume fraction
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201 11 of the second one (here cyanobacteria) within the suspension.
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$$\mu_r = \mu_0 \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\phi_m}{\phi_m^2} \right) \phi_1 \right) \phi_1 \right)^{-\alpha} \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\phi_m}{\phi_m^2} \right) \phi_2 \right) \phi_2 \right)^{-\alpha} \dots\dots (Eq. 7)$$

203 20 In all the viscosity models, α corresponds to the suspension's intrinsic viscosity, representing the impact of
21
22 suspending material on the effective viscosity increase. It is the fitted parameter and is determined using the
204 23 `curve_fit` function from the Python package SciPy (Virtanen, Gommers et al. 2020).
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206 28 **2.5.3 Statistical analysis** 29 30 31

207 32 Unless otherwise stated, all measurements were performed in triplicate, and the reported values are the
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208 34 averages of these replicates. The standard deviation was calculated using Pandas in Python (McKinney 2010).
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209 37 The R² score, calculated using scikit-learn (Pedregosa, Varoquaux et al. 2011), is reported for each model fit.
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210 39 The Pal23 model has an overall R² score calculated using all the data, an algae R² score for algae-only
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211 41 suspensions, a bacteria R² score for bacteria-only suspensions, and a mixed R² score for mixed suspensions.
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212 44 This approach allows to compare the Pal23 model fit quality to the mono-culture models (Einstein and
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213 46 Krieger-Dougherty).
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214 50 **3.0 Results** 51 52 53

215 54 **3.1 Algae and cyanobacteria morphology** 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

216 The morphology of the selected algae and cyanobacteria strains, as studied by microscopic image analysis
 217 (Supplementary Figure S1), is reported in Table 1. All species were approximately spherical, with aspect
 218 ratios ranging from 1.08 to 1.20. *Prochlorococcus* sp. had the smallest diameter of 0.72 μm , while *N. oceanica*,
 219 *C. vulgaris*, and *M. aeruginosa* had diameters of 2.77 μm , 3.99 μm , and 4.13 μm , respectively.

220 **Table 1: Morphological properties of algae and cyanobacteria species**

Species	Minor axis (μm)	Major axis (μm)	Cell volume (μm^3)	Aspect ratio	Effective diameter (μm)	Co-culture size ratio
Freshwater Co-culture						
<i>C. vulgaris</i>	3.87	4.24	33.33	1.10	3.99	0.97
<i>M. aeruginosa</i>	4.03	4.34	36.96	1.08	4.13	
Marine Co-culture						
<i>N. oceanica</i>	2.60	3.13	11.07	1.20	2.77	3.85
<i>Prochlorococcus</i> sp.	0.69	0.80	0.1989	1.16	0.72	

221 All strains except *Prochlorococcus* sp. have diameters large enough that Brownian motion is negligible. The
 222 smaller size of *Prochlorococcus* sp. suggests that physico-chemical interactions, rather than size, influence its
 223 rheological properties. In freshwater conditions, the size ratio between the two species is close to unity, so any
 224 rheological interplay is not attributable to conventional polydisperse suspension mechanisms (Pednekar, Chun
 225 et al. 2018).

3.2 Zeta potential

227 These mono- and mixed-species suspensions were used to investigate zeta potential measurements to
 228 understand cell-cell interactions (Supplementary Figure S2A and S2B). The monocultures of each species in

229 the defined ratios using their respective diluents were also tested. The two microalgae species, *C. vulgaris* and
230 ¹ *N. oceanica*, maintained stable zeta potential values regardless of cell concentration, ranging from 20.2 mV
231 ² to 21.9 mV and 13.9 mV to 16.0 mV, respectively. The cyanobacteria species, *M. aeruginosa* and
232 ³ *Prochlorococcus* sp., showed a decrease in zeta potential with increasing cell concentration. *M. aeruginosa*
233 ⁴ decreased from 33.03 mV to 24.5 mV, while *Prochlorococcus* sp. decreased from 17.9 mV to 12.8 mV. The
234 ⁵ zeta potential of mixed suspensions was primarily influenced by the concentration of cyanobacteria. In marine
235 ⁶ mixed suspensions (*N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp.), the zeta potential resembled that of *N. oceanica*
236 ⁷ due to the relatively low cell count of *Prochlorococcus* sp. in all the concentrations tested (Supplementary
237 ⁸ Table S2). In freshwater mixed suspensions (*C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*), high concentrations of *M.*
238 ⁹ *aeruginosa* (> 40% *M. aeruginosa*/*C. vulgaris* volume) resulted in higher zeta potential compared to *C.*
239 ¹⁰ *vulgaris* and mixed suspensions with lower *M. aeruginosa* concentrations ($\leq 10\%$ *M. aeruginosa*/*C. vulgaris*
240 ¹¹ volume).
241 ¹²

241 ¹³ **3.3 Rheology of mono- and mixed- cultures**

242 ¹⁴ Cell pellets for each species were obtained by centrifuging the cultures. The resulting supernatants were also
243 ¹⁵ stored to investigate viscosity as a function of the applied shear rate (Supplementary Figure S3), tested against
244 ¹⁶ fresh media (MLA, Pro99, and F/2) and diluents (MilliQ and 3% NaCl). The viscosity of MilliQ and 3% NaCl
245 ¹⁷ stabilized at a shear rate of 15 s^{-1} . Therefore, all values below this shear rate were removed from the analysis,
246 ¹⁸ as any viscosity variation before this point was attributed to experimental error, which is typically expected
247 ¹⁹ when measuring the viscosity of low-viscosity fluids in plate-plate geometries (Ewoldt, Johnston et al. 2015).
248 ²⁰ The supernatants of freshwater species *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa* had constant viscosities of 0.829 mPa·s
249 ²¹ and 0.841 mPa·s, respectively, similar to MilliQ and MLA (0.817 mPa·s and 0.824 mPa·s). The supernatants
250 ²² of *N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp. were more viscous (0.879 mPa·s and 0.878 mPa·s) than their
251 ²³ suspending diluents (3% NaCl, 0.846 mPa·s) and respective media (F/2 at 0.869 mPa·s and Pro99 at 0.809
252 ²⁴ mPa·s).
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253 Fixed quantities of cyanobacteria and microalgae cells were mixed to assess their combined impact on
 254 1 viscosity, compared to controls using MilliQ and 3% NaCl. Cell concentrations varied: *C. vulgaris* (8.61 to
 255 2 81.27×10^7 cells/mL), *M. aeruginosa* (0.69 to 8.0×10^7 cells/mL), *N. oceanica* (13.29 to 136.4×10^7 cells/mL),
 256 3 and *Prochlorococcus* sp. (0.47 to 6.1×10^7 cells/mL). Supplementary Table S2 detailed cell concentrations,
 257 4 volume fractions, power-law model parameters (Eq. 3), and viscosity at 100 s^{-1} shear rates. *C. vulgaris*
 258 5 (Supplementary Figure S4A), *N. oceanica* (S4C), and *Prochlorococcus* sp. (S4D) exhibited Newtonian
 259 6 behavior across shear rates. A slight decrease in flow behavior index below 1.00 with higher cell concentration
 260 7 was observed but did not indicate significant shear-thinning. *M. aeruginosa* (S4B) showed obvious shear-
 261 8 thinning behavior as cell concentration increased above 4.30×10^7 cells/mL ($\phi = 0.001590$), with the flow
 262 9 behavior index decreasing from 0.88 to 0.70 at 11.77×10^7 cells/mL ($\phi = 0.004351$).

263 10 All suspensions of microalgae and cyanobacteria were fitted with the Einstein & Krieger-Dougherty models
 264 11 (Figure 1). As cell concentration increased, the viscosity of freshwater *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*
 265 12 suspensions also increased. *C. vulgaris* viscosity increased from 0.81 mPa·s to 0.97 mPa·s at 100 s^{-1} across
 266 13 the tested concentrations, while *M. aeruginosa* viscosity increased more significantly from 0.85 mPa·s to 2.24
 267 14 mPa·s at the same shear rate.

270 **Figure 1** Relative viscosity of freshwater species (A, *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*) and marine species (B,
271 *N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp.) suspended in MLA and 3% NaCl, respectively. The results are
272 represented as average and standard deviation of three replicates.

273 Figure 1A depicted the relative viscosity as a function of the total volume fraction occupied by both species,
274 fitted with the Einstein & Krieger-Dougherty models. The intrinsic viscosities were 7.28 and 310.05 for the
275 Einstein model, and 6.56 and 210.51 for the Krieger-Dougherty model, representing *C. vulgaris* and *M.*
276 *aeruginosa*, respectively. The Krieger-Dougherty model suggested that *M. aeruginosa* viscosity could increase
277 exponentially as the volume fraction exceeds the tested range, whereas *C. vulgaris* viscosity did not
278 significantly deviate from the linear behavior predicted by the Einstein model within the explored range.

279 In case of marine species, both *N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp. exhibited increasing viscosity with higher
280 cell concentrations, measured from 0.87 mPa·s to 1.05 mPa·s and 0.914 mPa·s to 1.06 mPa·s respectively, at
281 a shear rate of 100 s⁻¹. The relative viscosity, compared to NaCl (3%) at 100 s⁻¹, varied with the total volume
282 fraction occupied by each species (Figure 1B). *Prochlorococcus* sp. demonstrated significantly higher intrinsic
283 viscosity compared to *N. oceanica* and freshwater species across tested concentrations. The Einstein and
284 Krieger-Dougherty models provided intrinsic viscosity values, highlighting differences between *N. oceanica*
285 (17.71 and 15.64) and *Prochlorococcus* sp. (23093.66 and 20439.85). The cell concentrations, volume
286 fractions, viscosity at a shear rate of 100 s⁻¹, and power-law parameters for mixed suspensions are detailed in
287 Supplementary Table S2.

288 The rheology of both marine and freshwater mixed suspensions was found to be influenced more by the
289 combination of microalgae and cyanobacteria rather than by their individual concentrations (Figure 2). The
290 freshwater mixed suspensions (Figure 2A) consistently showed shear thinning behavior, even at the lowest
291 concentration of *M. aeruginosa*. The flow behavior index decreased from 0.96 to 0.72, while the consistency
292 index increased as the flow behavior index decreased, ranging from 1.22 mPa·sⁿ to 8.18 mPa·sⁿ. In contrast,
293 the viscosity of marine mixed suspensions depended on the overall mixture of *N. oceanica* and

294 *Prochlorococcus* sp., rather than on the specific ratio of these species (Figure 2B). The marine mixed
 295 1 suspensions exhibited rheological behavior like their individual components, with a minor decrease in the
 296 2 flow behavior index (-0.01). However, proper shear thinning behavior was not observed due to the low volume
 297 3 fractions tested. The consistency index ranged from 1.15 mPa·sⁿ to 1.26 mPa·sⁿ.

299 27 **Figure 2** Flow behavior of freshwater species (A, *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*) and marine species (B, *N.*
 298 28 *oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp.) prepared in a known ratio of cell concentration. The results are the average
 299 29 and standard deviation of three replicates, fitted using the power-law model.

3.4 Modified model for rheology parameters

303 39 Neither the Einstein nor the Krieger-Dougherty models could adequately fit the viscosity data for both
 304 40 freshwater and marine mixed suspensions, as indicated by negative R^2 values for both suspensions. This
 305 41 indicated that viscosity was not solely dependent on the total volume fraction but instead on a combination of
 306 42 both microalgae and cyanobacteria. While we were within the dilute concentration range where the Einstein
 307 43 model is applicable to individual suspension viscosities, we considered mixed models based on a Krieger-
 308 44 Dougherty structure for several reasons: the existing Pal23 model in the literature already uses this approach,
 309 45 it accounts for possible non-linear behavior when combining species, and it allows for further generalization
 310 46 of our work to larger volume fractions that deviate from Einstein behaviors.

311 Therefore, we used a novel Pal23 model (Eq. 7) to understand the rheological parameters of mixed particle
 312 1 types. However, the original Pal23 model also proved to be a poor fit for the data, as shown in Figures 3A and
 313 2 3B, with negative R² values for both freshwater and mixed suspensions. The poor performance was due to the
 314 3 4 model's constraint of equal intrinsic viscosity for both species, which failed to capture the substantial
 315 5 6 differences in viscosity sensitivity to volume fractions among the various species, as shown in the monoculture
 316 7 8 results in Figure 1.

317 9 Thus, a modified Pal23 Model was developed, incorporating two independent intrinsic viscosity terms (α_1 &
 318 10 α_2), as depicted in Figures 3C and 3D, and Eq. 8.

$$\mu_r = \mu_0 \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\phi_m}{\phi_m^2} \right) \phi_1 \right) \phi_1 \right)^{-a_1} \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{1-\phi_m}{\phi_m^2} \right) \phi_2 \right) \phi_2 \right)^{-a_2} \dots\dots\dots \text{(Eq. 8)}$$

320 11 This model showed improved fitting for both freshwater and marine mono-species suspensions. In the
 321 12 13 freshwater suspension, both mono- and mixed-species showed a good R² value. However, for marine
 322 14 15 suspensions, while an overall positive R² was attained for mono-species, the mixed-species data still showed
 323 16 17 a negative R² value.

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Figure 3 Relative viscosity of freshwater species (A, *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*) and marine species (B, *N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus sp.*) using the Pal23 model (Eq. 7). A modified version of the Pal23 model (Eq. 8) was also applied to both freshwater (C) and marine (D) species. The results represent the average and standard deviation of three replicates.

Visual examination of the freshwater model revealed that it failed to predict the viscosity reduction observed in the three most *M. aeruginosa* dense mixed suspensions, although it effectively accounted for viscosity increases in *C. vulgaris* dense suspensions. In contrast, the marine model consistently overpredicted viscosity for mixed suspensions. The intrinsic viscosity values from the modified Pal23 model, α_1 & α_2 , did not exactly

335 match those from the Einstein model but were similar to those from the Krieger-Dougherty model. For the
336 1 freshwater suspension, α_1 & α_2 were 6.69 and 203.51, respectively, while for the marine suspension, α_1 & α_2
337 2 were 14.70 and 18240.23, respectively. The proximity of the intrinsic viscosity values determined from the
338 3 Krieger-Dougherty model to those of the modified Pal23 model suggests that the viscosity of suspensions
339 4 containing two cells with different particle-fluid interactions could be predicted using this modified Pal23
340 5 model, at least in the dilute range as was investigated in this study.

341 15 **4.0 Discussion**

342 17 The lack of shear thinning observed in *C. vulgaris*, *N. oceanica*, and *Prochlorococcus* sp. in this study
343 18 (Supplementary Figure S4A, S4C, S4D) is most likely attributable to the low volume fractions tested. These
344 19 low volume fractions would have limited the effects of particle-particle interactions on the flow behavior of
345 20 these suspensions. Previous research has reported shear thinning in suspensions containing *C. vulgaris* and
346 21 *Nannochloropsis* sp., but only at higher concentrations ($\phi > 0.06$ and $\phi > 0.04$, respectively) (Wileman,
347 22 Ozkan et al. 2012) than those tested here. In such cases, the concentration typically exceeds the dilute limit
348 23 defined by Einstein (Barnes 2000), where particle-particle interactions begin to significantly influence
349 24 rheological behavior (Martínez-Sanz, Garrido-Fernández et al. 2020). Although the study does not investigate
350 25 the non-Newtonian rheology of denser suspensions found in advanced PBRs (Dogaris, Welch et al. 2015), it
351 26 is noted that current industrial settings typically operate with very dilute suspensions densities (Muhammad,
352 27 Alam et al. 2020), making the findings highly relevant to existing industrial applications.

353 45 Our findings indicate that *M. aeruginosa* displayed shear thinning at cell concentrations exceeding 4.3×10^7
354 46 cells/mL (Supplementary Figure S4B). This suggests that at higher concentrations, this organism begins to be
355 47 affected by the shear rate, leading to a change in the particle-fluid interactions (Mewis and Wagner 2011). This
356 48 behavior was also evident in mixed suspensions of *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa*, which exhibited shear
357 49 thinning across all tested concentrations (Figure 2A). This implies that at the lowest concentrations,
358 50 interactions between *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa* cells promote non-Newtonian behavior, which does not
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359 occur in low concentrations of *M. aeruginosa* or in any concentration of *C. vulgaris*. No prior research on the
360 1 rheology of *Prochlorococcus* sp. could be found, but since we tested concentrations below the dilute limit,
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361 4 shear thinning due to particle-particle interactions was not expected. The rheology of *Prochlorococcus* sp. can
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362 6 be compared to the closely related *Synechococcus* sp., which showed shear thinning at a volume fraction of
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363 8 0.087 (Song, Kang et al. 2018).
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364 12 Increased viscosity with increasing cell concentration was expected for all species tested. This is well-
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365 14 documented for microalgae like *C. vulgaris* (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012, Souliès, Pruvost et al. 2013) and *N.*
366 15
366 16 *oceanica* (Wileman, Ozkan et al. 2012, Attar, Morillas-Espana et al. 2022). Although this is the first study on
367 17
367 18 the topic for the cyanobacteria, the increase in viscosity was expected since neither species is motile (Coe,
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367 20 Ghizzoni et al. 2016), and motility can increase the viscosity (Rafai, Jibuti et al. 2010, Cagney, Zhang et al.
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368 22 2017). An increase in viscosity is expected when studying the rheology of microalgae due to factors such as
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369 24 zeta potential (Zhang, Jiang et al. 2013), morphologies (Cagney, Zhang et al. 2017), exopolymeric substance
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370 26 (EPS) characteristics (Belachqer-El Attar, Morillas-Espana et al. 2023), and cultivation conditions (Chen,
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371 28 Chen et al. 1997). Previous research has shown that EPS production in *C. vulgaris* increases suspension
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372 30 viscosity and also causes shear thinning behavior (El-Naggar, Hussein et al. 2020). EPS production and
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373 32 characteristics vary by species, strain, and conditions (Baroni 2019), with *Microcystis* sp. producing more
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374 34 viscous EPS than other cyanobacteria and microalgae (Mancuso Nichols, Nairn et al. 2009). The shear-
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375 36 thinning behavior of *M. aeruginosa* could be partly due to the bound EPS on the cells, which has been observed
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376 38 to be shear-thinning in other species (Laroche 2022).
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378 42 The supernatants of *C. vulgaris* and *M. aeruginosa* had similar viscosities to media blanks (Supplementary
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379 44 Figure S3), indicating low dissolved EPS. In contrast, *N. oceanica* and *Prochlorococcus* sp. supernatants were
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380 46 more viscous than their media blanks (Supplementary Figure S3), suggesting significant dissolved EPS. With
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381 48 no published data available on rheology of *Prochlorococcus* sp., it is difficult to confidently explain the high
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382 50 intrinsic viscosity observed in this current study (Supplementary Figure S3). While, EPS measurement was
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383 not within the scope of this study, future work investigating rheology of *Prochlorococcus* sp. and including
384 EPS measurement have the potential to clarify the cause of this high intrinsic viscosity.

385 The zeta potential of these species was considered in this study. The Smoluchowski factor (S_f , Supplementary
386 Equations SE1 and SE2) quantifies the increase in cell volume fraction (ϕ) within a suspension (Bird, Stewart
387 et al. 2002). This increased volume fraction can then be applied to the viscosity models to describe the effect
388 of zeta potential. Due to the larger size (Table 1) and similar zeta potential (Supplementary Figure S2) values
389 of *C. vulgaris*, *M. aeruginosa*, and *N. oceanica*, there was little difference in the Smoluchowski factor
390 (Supplementary Table S3). In contrast, due to the much smaller size of *Prochlorococcus* sp. (Table 1), the
391 difference in the Smoluchowski factor was more pronounced compared to the other three species
392 (Supplementary Table S3). This partially explains why *Prochlorococcus* sp. exhibited such a high intrinsic
393 viscosity (Figure 1B). However, the exact mechanism behind the viscosity increase in *Prochlorococcus* sp.
394 remains unclear. Further research is necessary to understand *Prochlorococcus* sp. implications in co-culture
395 systems fully.

396 The Einstein and Krieger-Dougherty models describe the relationship between relative viscosity and volume
397 fraction (ϕ) within measurement uncertainty. The intrinsic viscosities of *C. vulgaris* and *N. oceanica* are
398 relatively similar, while those of *M. aeruginosa* and *Prochlorococcus* sp. are significantly higher (Figure 1).
399 *C. vulgaris* has the most similar intrinsic viscosity to the Einstein model (Barnes 2000), which aligns with its
400 lack of significant EPS production, low Smoluchowski factor, and rigid cell wall, making it closest to
401 suspensions of rigid spheres for which the theory was derived. The application of the Power Law model
402 (Supplementary Figure S4) to monocultures revealed no shear thinning for *C. vulgaris*, *N. oceanica*, and
403 *Prochlorococcus* sp., further supporting that the volume fractions tested were below the threshold where
404 particle interactions significantly impact viscosity. However, the viscosity in mixed suspensions did not
405 correlate with total volume fraction (Figure 2), highlighting the limitations of conventional models like
406 Einstein and Krieger-Dougherty, which are optimized for mono-species scenarios. A novel Pal23 model (Eq.

407 7) was used to fit the data in mixed-species scenario considering two different volume fractions (ϕ_1 , ϕ_2)
408 1 (Figure 3A-D). However, one potential issue with this model is the assumption that both particle types have
409 4 the same intrinsic viscosity and impact on viscosity with increasing volume fraction. This is not true for
410 6 different microalgae species and strains, as shown by (Cagney, Zhang et al. 2017) and (Zhang, Jiang et al.
411 9 2013).

412 12 However, in our study, all three models (the Einstein, Krieger-Dougherty, and Pal23) failed to accurately
413 15 predict the viscosity of mixed suspensions, primarily due to the disproportionate influence of low-volume-
414 17 fraction cyanobacteria on overall suspension viscosity. In mixed suspensions with particles having different
415 20 intrinsic viscosities, the Pal23 model would fail to predict the relative viscosity accurately. To overcome this
416 22 limitation, the current study modified the Pal23 model (Eq. 8), incorporating two independent volume fraction
417 25 terms for different particle types, provided a more accurate understanding of the viscosity in mixed
418 27 suspensions.

419 30 Cyanobacteria, with their inherently higher viscosity per unit volume fraction compared to microalgae (Figure
420 33 1B), significantly affected suspension rheology when combined. This divergence from expected model
421 35 predictions underscores the complex interplay of components in mixed suspensions, where simple volume
422 38 fraction-viscosity relationships do not hold when one component dominates rheological behavior, such as
423 40 observed with *Prochlorococcus sp.* (Figure 3D).

424 44 Notably, in highly concentrated *Prochlorococcus sp.* mixed suspensions, rheological behavior mirrored that
425 46 of pure *Prochlorococcus sp.* suspensions (Figure 3D), indicating minimal impact from the added *N. oceanica*
426 49 despite increased volume fraction. However, in less concentrated *Prochlorococcus sp.* cultures, the influence
427 51 of *N. oceanica* on rheology became more apparent (Figure 3D). This rheological behavior aligns with
428 53 expectations that increasing volume fraction generally increases viscosity, yet it also highlights the significant
429 56 role of dominant species in determining overall suspension viscosity.

430 Conversely, in freshwater mixed suspensions (Figure 3C) with higher *M. aeruginosa* concentrations, viscosity
431 1 decreased compared to pure *M. aeruginosa* (Figure 1A) suspensions, even with the increase in volume fraction
432 2 from the added *C. vulgaris*. This unexpected decrease challenges conventional rheological expectations,
433 3 suggesting additional factors at play beyond volume fraction alone. Variations in zeta potential with changing
434 4 concentration and the differential EPS characteristics of cyanobacteria likely contribute to these observed
435 5 rheological complexities, suggesting further investigation into their specific impacts.

436 15 **5.0 Conclusion**

437 18 The current study investigated the rheological dynamics of co-cultivating algae and cyanobacteria. The study
438 19 aimed to bridge the gaps in understanding for more efficient and scalable algal cultivations by investigating
439 20 into species-specific morphology, zeta potential, and flow behavior and rheology of mixed-species
440 21 suspensions. Traditional viscosity models (Einstein, Krieger-Dougherty) did not accurately predict mixed
441 22 suspension viscosity. The modified Pal23 model provided a more accurate fit, highlighting the need for better
442 23 designed rheological models. Overall, cyanobacteria applied a disproportionate influence on suspension
443 24 viscosity in mixed cultures, challenging simple volume fraction-viscosity relationships. By addressing the
444 25 complexities of mixed-species suspensions, our research highlights the need for better designed rheological
445 26 models that account for species-specific interactions and concentration-dependent behaviors. Future research
446 27 should aim to explore higher biomass densities and a broader range of shear rates to better understand the
447 28 industrial-scale implications of these findings.

448 46 **Acknowledgements**

449 48 The authors acknowledge the support of the Climate Change Cluster at the University of Technology Sydney
450 49 for their assistance in supporting the Honours research program.

451 54 **CRedit Author Statement**

452 **CB:** methodology, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing-original draft; **NP:** conceptualization,
453 1 methodology, formal analysis, writing - original draft, supervision, project administration; **TL:** formal
454 2 analysis, writing – review and editing; **MP:** supervision, writing - review and editing; **VG:** supervision,
455 3 writing – review and editing; **LA:** resources, writing - review and editing; **UK:** resources, writing - review
456 4 and editing; **PJR:** funding acquisition, writing - review and editing.

457 12 **Conflict of Interest**

458 13 Authors declare no conflict of interest.

459 18 **Declaration**

460 22 During the preparation of this work the authors used BioRender tool in order to create high quality graphical
461 24 abstract. Publication licence is attached with this manuscript. Authors also used Chatgpt tool to improve the
462 26 readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content
463 28 as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article. No other tools or services were
464 30 used for this manuscript.

465 35 **References**

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